

COURSE OF CORONAVIRUS INFECTION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS C

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Abstract. A study was conducted on 62 patients with COVID-19, aged 23 to 42 years. The diagnostic criteria for identifying COVID-19 and its impact on liver function in chronic viral hepatitis C were studied. Among the patients, 61.3% were male, and 38.7% were female. Virus shedding typically lasted up to 12 days in the lungs, and in moderate to severe cases, it extended beyond 14 days. Pneumonia was the leading clinical form of COVID-19 in 15 patients. The diagnosis of pneumonia in COVID-19 was based on epidemiological history, clinical examination, and laboratory and instrumental methods. In patients with COVID-19 and chronic viral hepatitis C, the manifestation of the intoxication syndrome was more pronounced than in patients without underlying liver pathology. The course of COVID-19 in chronic hepatitis was characterized by a cholestatic component and pronounced hepatocellular changes in the liver, with elevated liver function test results.

Keywords: radiological and CT scans, airborne droplets, C-reactive protein, headache, nausea and vomiting.

Introduction. Coronaviruses are widespread in nature and are causes of various common colds (up to 25% of cases). Most of them cause viral infections that do not seriously harm health, but some, such as SARS-CoV (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus) and MERS-CoV (Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus), lead to the development of severe respiratory syndrome with high mortality rates [1,2].

Previous studies have shown that SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV cause liver damage in infected patients. In cases of COVID-19, abnormalities in liver function were also detected, which were associated with the progression and severity of the infectious process [3,4]. The effects of SARS-CoV-2 on the course and outcomes of chronic liver diseases have also been studied [5,6,7].

Research methods. A study was conducted on 62 patients with COVID-19, aged 23 to 42 years, at City Clinical Infectious Diseases Hospital No. 5 in Tashkent. The diagnostic criteria for identifying COVID-19 and its impact on liver function in chronic viral hepatitis C were studied. Among the patients, 61.3% were male, and 38.7% were female. COVID-19 was diagnosed based on PCR analysis and the clinical course of the disease. The levels of transaminases (ALT, AST), thymol test, bilirubin and its fractions in blood serum, thymol and mercuric chloride tests, and liver ultrasound were used to assess liver function. Lung tissue damage was evaluated using chest CT scans.

Epidemiological data indicated that patients with cardiovascular diseases, arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus, malignant tumors, and chronic liver disease are the most susceptible to coronavirus infection. The incubation period ranged from 2 to 14 days (with an average period of 5-6 days). COVID-19 was transmitted by airborne droplets (during coughing, sneezing, talking), airborne dust (through airborne dust particles), contact (through handshakes, household items), and fecal-oral routes

Research results. Virus shedding typically lasted up to 12 days, and in moderate to severe cases, it extended beyond 14 days. It was noted that most patients exhibited biochemical changes, and in 2-11% of cases, the infection developed against a background of chronic liver disease (CLD). The increase in ALT/AST (alanine and aspartate aminotransferase) activity generally exceeded 1.5-2 times the upper limit of normal and was accompanied by a slight increase in total bilirubin levels.

In response to the spread of the coronavirus, a hyperimmune reaction, known as a “cytokine storm,” was observed, characterized by the synthesis of a significant (abnormal) amount of pro-inflammatory interleukins.

Discussion. Pneumonia was the primary clinical form of COVID-19 in 15 patients. The diagnosis of COVID-19-related pneumonia was based on epidemiological history, clinical examination, and laboratory and instrumental methods.

Radiological and CT scans of the lungs revealed ground-glass opacities, infiltrates in various lobes, and interstitial changes. Laboratory findings associated with this infection included leukopenia, lymphopenia, thrombocytopenia, and elevated C-reactive protein (CRP). Laboratory tests also showed abnormalities in liver function, which were associated with the progression and severity of the infection.

The main clinical symptoms are presented in Table 1.

Main symptoms	Mild course	Moderate-severe course	Severe course
Increase in body temperature to 38-39 C	12 (19.4%)	20 (32.2%)	30 (48.4%)
Cough	10 (16.1%)	28 (45.1)	26 (41.9%)
Felling of chest tightness	-	14 (22.6%)	38 (61.3%)
Shortness of breath	-	20 (32.3%)	42 (67.7%)
Muscle and headache	3 (4.8%)	26 (41.9)	33 (53.2%)
Nausea and vomiting	-	18 (29%)	44 (71%)
Loss of appetite	9 (14.6%)	21 (33.9%)	32 (51.6%)

The most common symptoms of the infection were as follows: fever, cough, chills, shortness of breath, muscle and headache, nausea and vomiting, and loss of appetite. The average duration of symptoms was 5 days. In moderate and severe cases of the disease, some changes in biochemical blood parameters were observed.

The methods used, including hydroxychloroquine, antibiotics, and antiviral drugs, may exacerbate liver damage due to their potential hepatotoxicity. As a result, hydroxychloroquine was excluded from the therapy for patients.

Conclusions.

In patients with COVID-19 against the background of chronic viral hepatitis C, the manifestation of the intoxication syndrome is more pronounced than in patients without underlying liver pathology.

The course of COVID-19 in chronic hepatitis is characterized by a cholestatic component and pronounced hepatocellular changes in the liver, with elevated liver function test results. Patients who have recovered from a coronavirus infection require continued outpatient monitoring to restore impaired liver function.

REFERENCES

1. Cao X. COVID- 19: immunopathology and its implications for therapy /Nature reviews immunology. - 2020. - T. 20. - No. 5. - C. 269-270.
2. Fauci A. S., Lane H. C., Redfield R. R. COVID-19 navigating the uncharted. - 2020.
3. Sabirovich ½. A. Et al. Functional status of kidneys, immune and antioxidant systems in children with chronic hepatitis with related chronic pyelonephritis //journal of critical reviews. - 2020. - I. 7. - No. 17. - c. 2176-2182.
4. Baibosynov D. M., Iginov N. S., Kuljanova Sh. A. Spatiotemporal assessment of hepatitis A morbidity in the population of Kazakhstan // Medicine (Almaty). - 2018. - No. 5. - P. 35-39.
5. Yusupov A. S., Faiziev B. O., Karimova D. U. Cellular immunity indicators in patients with hepatitis C // Current Issues in Modern Science. - 2019. - No. 2/3. - P. 45-49.
6. Yusupov A. S., Faiziev B. O., Tashpulatov S. A. Changes in the immune system in toxicosis caused by chronic viral hepatitis in the context of chronic pyelonephritis // Science of the 21st Century - A Look into the Future. - 2018. - P. 115-119.
7. Rakhimov B. O., Yusupov A. S., Metabolic changes in hepatitis A with functional nephropathy in children // The Modern World: Experience, Problems, and Prospects for Development. - 2018. - Vol. 2. - No. 1. - P. 3-6
8. Yusupov A. S. ARVI in Children with Hepatitis A: Clinical Course// Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences (EJMNS) 30.04.2024